

Heterobinuclear Complexes of Transition Metals involving Unsymmetrical Quadridentate Schiff Base

B. T. THAKER

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

Manuscript received 30 December 1985, revised 11 September 1986, accepted 17 February 1987

Copper(II)-M(II) binuclear complexes, $[(\text{Cu-QSB-}o\text{-PhDA})\text{MX}_2]$, (M = Co, Zn, Cd, Hg; X = Cl, Br) have been prepared and characterised, where QSB-*o*-PhDA represents *N,N'*-*o*-phenylene[1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)-ethylideneamine, -salicylideneamine or -2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneamine] and *N,N'*-*o*-phenylene(salicylidene amine, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneamine). Ligand field bands due to the copper(II) ion bound at $[\text{N}_2\text{O}_2]$ coordinating site in $[(\text{Cu-QSB-}o\text{-PhDA})\text{MX}_2]$ are blue-shifted relative to the mononuclear complex (Cu-QSB-*o*-PhDA). This suggests that the CuN_2O_2 moiety becomes more planar when (Cu-QSB-*o*-PhDA) coordinates to MX_2 with the phenolic oxygen atoms. The heterobinuclear complexes have been characterised by elemental analyses, reflectance and infrared spectral and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

COOPERATIVE interaction between metal ions and their influence on reactivity are subjects of considerable current interest. In order to assess carefully the nature of the cooperativity and the reactivity, several workers have designed new ligand systems capable of binding more than one metal ion and used them to prepare polynuclear metal complexes of a discrete molecular nature. Schiff base complexes have been particularly valuable for designing complexes of widely differing structural type¹⁻³. Recently homobinuclear copper(II) complexes involving tridentate⁴⁻⁷, tetradentate⁸⁻¹⁰ and pentadentate Schiff base^{11,12} have been synthesised and characterised with the special interest of electrochemical properties.

Solutions of various metal--salicylaldimines (1) and metal halides react in organic solvents to form polynuclear complexes to which Gruber *et al.*¹³ attributed an oxygen bridged structure (2). Similarly, unsymmetrical bifunctional tetradentate

Schiff base complexes (3) and other metal halides or metal perchlorate react in organic solvents homo or hetero polynuclear complex (4).

Oxygen bridging of the type shown in structure 2 and 4 bring groups of two or three metal atoms into close proximity so that antiferromagnetic interactions occur in a number of cases where the metals have unpaired electrons. In the complexes of type 2, the complex ligands have two phenolic oxygens in the *cis*-position and are forced to act as bidentates. It was observed by Harris and Sinn¹⁴ that if one of the metal ions is in a planar environment, the adjacent metal ion will be distorted away from planarity. It was also reported by Muto *et al.*^{15,16} that in binuclear copper(II) complexes with tridentate salicylaldehyde Schiff bases, the geometry around the atom bridging metal ions is one of the most important factors determining the strength and sign of the magnetic interaction. These factors may bring about an increase in overlap of the non-orthogonal orbitals involved in the exchange pathways. Similarly, Glick and Lintvedt¹⁷ noted the importance of the planarity of the bridging atom in binuclear copper(II) complexes for magnetic interaction. In this type of polynuclear complexes since one metal atom is inside the Schiff base and the other outside it, so that even for homo- or hetero-nuclear complexes, the environment about each of the metal atoms are different. The environment about each of the metal atoms can be varied by varying the Schiff bases, the other ligands and chainlength between two nitrogen atoms of the complex ligands.

It was, therefore, thought of interest to study the coordination of quadridentate Schiff base complexes of copper(II) with a different metal halides.

This paper reports the preparation of heterobinuclear complexes of the type $[(\text{Cu-QSB-}o\text{-PhDA})\text{MX}_2]$, where QSB-*o*-PhDA = the quadridentate Schiff bases *N,N'*-*o*-phenylene[1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethylideneamine, -salicylideneamine] (QSB-1-*o*-PhDA), *N,N'*-*o*-phenylene[1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethylideneamine, -2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneamine] (QSB-2-*o*-PhDA) or *N,N'*-*o*-phenylene(salicylideneamine 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneamine) (QSB-3-*o*-PhDA), where $M = \text{Co, Zn, Cd, Hg}$; $X = \text{Cl or Br}$. An attempt has been made to study the electronic spectra and magnetic properties of such compounds and to see the presence of (M^{2+}) other metal ion, there is any effect on environment of Cu^{2+} atom.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The following three parent Schiff base complexes (A-C) used for reactions with MX_2 were prepared according to published procedure¹⁸: (A) *N,N'*-*o*-phenylene[1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethylideneaminato, salicylideneaminato]copper(II), (B) *N,N'*-*o*-phenylene[1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethylideneaminato, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneaminato]copper(II), and (C) *N,N'*-*o*-phenylene(salicylideneaminato, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneaminato)copper(II).

Preparation of $(\text{Cu-QSB-}o\text{-PhDA})\text{MX}_2$ ($M = \text{Co, Zn, Cd, Hg}$; $X = \text{Cl or Br}$): Compound A, B or C (Cu-QSB-*o*-PhDA) (0.04 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) containing CoCl_2 , HgCl_2 , CdBr_2 ,

ZnCl_2 or ZnBr_2 (0.043 mol) was refluxed for 6 h, and then the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The solid complexes obtained in each case was collected by filtration, washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried in vacuum. For the preparation of $[(\text{Cu-QSB-}o\text{-PhDA})\text{CoCl}_2]$, anhydrous CoCl_2 prepared by heating $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in an oven was used.

The analyses and magnetic moment data of the complexes are reported in Table I. The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were measured at room temperature by the Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 427 grating spectrophotometer. The diffuse reflectance measurements were made on a Beckman-DU spectrophotometer.

The binuclear complexes are not sufficiently soluble in organic solvents than the complex ligands, hence their molar conductance could not be determined.

Results and Discussion

$[(\text{Cu-QSB-}o\text{-PhDA})\text{CuX}_2]$, homobinuclear complexes have been synthesised¹⁹, where $X = \text{Cl or ClO}_4$. QSB-*o*-PhDA is an unsymmetrical quadridentate Schiff base. These unsymmetrical quadridentate Schiff bases were prepared by template synthesis followed by amine exchange. Similarly, reaction of unsymmetrical quadridentate aromatic diamine Schiff base complexes of copper(II) (A), (B) (C) with MX_2 (where $M = \text{Co, Zn, Cd, Hg}$; $X = \text{Cl or Br}$) yielded heterobinuclear complexes Cu (A or B or C) MX_2 .

The planar complexes (Cu-QSB-*o*-PhDA) (A), (B) or (C) remain essentially planar when they act as complex ligands, but the second metal atom need not lie in the same plane as the first metal and its four donor atoms. The magnetic moment of $[(\text{Cu-QSB-1,2 and 3-}o\text{-PhDA})\text{CoCl}_2]$ is in the range 4.75–4.92 B.M. The magnetic moments of cobalt(II) in the above complexes indicate that the cobalt atom is almost in a tetrahedral rather than a planar environment^{20,21}. These moments are of the same order as the average value 4.8 B.M. observed for the CoCl_4^{2-} anion with a series of cations in the solid state²². The magnetic moments of other heterobinuclear complexes $[(\text{Cu-QSB-1,2 and 3-}o\text{-PhDA})\text{MX}_2]$ ($M = \text{Zn, Cd, Hg}$; $X = \text{Cl or Br}$) fall in the range 1.80–1.86 B.M. at room temperature. These values are quite reasonable since the second metal ion has no unpaired electron.

The band positions in the ligand field spectra of these complexes also show that the copper(II) in these bimolecular complexes is in a square planar geometry. The reflectance spectra of the parent mononuclear complex (A), (B) and (C) showed a broad d-d band at $17\,240 - 16\,666 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as expected for a square-planar copper(II) complex. The

TABLE I—ELEMENTAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS DATA OF COMPLEXES AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Compd.	Analysis % · Found(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
	N	Cu	Co	
Cu-QSB-1- <i>o</i> -PhDA- CoCl_2	5.42 (5.37)	12.05 (12.19)	11.25 (11.31)	4.75
Cu-QSB-1- <i>o</i> -PhDA- HgCl_2^*	—	9.70 (9.75)	—	1.82
Cu-QSB-1- <i>o</i> -PhDA- CdBr_2	4.35 (4.22)	9.42 (9.57)	—	1.84
Cu-QSB-1- <i>o</i> -PhDA- ZnCl_2	5.18 (5.30)	11.95 (12.04)	—	1.86
Cu-QSB-1- <i>o</i> -PhDA- ZnBr_2	4.00 (4.54)	11.12 (10.30)	—	1.83
Cu-QSB-2- <i>o</i> -PhDA- CoCl_2	4.68 (4.90)	11.25 (11.12)	10.50 (10.31)	4.90
Cu-QSB-2- <i>o</i> -PhDA- HgCl_2^*	—	8.85 (8.91)	—	1.83
Cu-QSB-2- <i>o</i> -PhDA- CdBr_2	3.85 (3.92)	8.95 (8.90)	—	1.84
Cu-QSB-2- <i>o</i> -PhDA- ZnCl_2	4.75 (4.84)	10.56 (10.99)	—	1.86
Cu-QSB-2- <i>o</i> -PhDA- ZnBr_2	4.05 (4.20)	9.42 (9.53)	—	1.85
Cu-QSB-3- <i>o</i> -PhDA- CoCl_2	5.12 (5.02)	11.55 (11.40)	10.60 (10.57)	4.84
Cu-QSB-3- <i>o</i> -PhDA- HgCl_2^*	—	9.15 (9.09)	—	1.84
Cu-QSB-3- <i>o</i> -PhDA- CdBr_2	3.95 (4.01)	8.98 (9.08)	—	1.86
Cu-QSB-3- <i>o</i> -PhDA- ZnCl_2	4.82 (4.95)	11.30 (11.27)	—	1.82
Cu-QSB-3- <i>o</i> -PhDA- ZnBr_2	4.35 (4.29)	9.65 (9.74)	—	1.85

*N analyses were not carried out because of the presence of Hg.

reflectance spectra of [(Cu-QSB-1,2 and 3-*o*-PhDA)CoCl₂] showed the bands at 15 350 and 14 800 cm⁻¹ in addition to the band at 17 400 cm⁻¹, which is due to the copper(II) ion at the N₂O₂ site. The former two bands are similar to that observed by Nakamura *et al.*²⁵. The 15 350 and 14 800 cm⁻¹ bands are due to the cobalt(II) ion, and judging from the band positions and intensities, the geometry around to cobalt(II) is nearly tetrahedral. The reflectance spectra of the [(Cu-QSB-1,2 and 3-*o*-PhDA)MX₂] (M=Zn, Cd, Hg; X=Cl, Br) complexes show one band of copper(II) ion in the region 17 240–17 700 cm⁻¹. The band maximum shifts to higher frequency compared with the mononuclear complex. Such a blue-shift of the d-d band was first observed by Gruber *et al.*²¹ in the [Cu(salen)-MX₂] complexes. The blue-shift of the d-d band of [(Cu-QSB-1,2 and 3-*o*-PhDA)MX₂] (M=Zn, Cd, Hg; X=Cl, Br) are in the order Zn > Cd > Hg. This trend can be explained by assuming that the (CuN₂O₂) chromophore becomes more planar when the mononuclear compound is linked with MX₂. Thus, it is understandable that this effect becomes large as the size of M²⁺ decreases.

Infrared spectral studies of binuclear complexes derived from quadridentate Schiff base complexes also support the formation of the binuclear complex^{14,25,26}. There is an increase in the frequency of the certain functional groups of the parent complexes on its coordination with MX₂. A characteristic in the infrared spectra of [(Cu-QSB-1,2 and 3-*o*-PhDA)MX₂] show an intense band in the range 1 550–1 555 cm⁻¹, while the band in the spectra of the parent complexes (Cu-QSB-1,2 or 3-*o*-PhDA) appears near 1 530 cm⁻¹. Shifting of this band towards higher frequencies (15–20 cm⁻¹) indicates the presence of bridging phenolic oxygen atoms in the binuclear complexes.

The difference between the mononuclear and the binuclear complexes is the bonding mode of the phenolic oxygen, the simple coordination in the former and the bridging in the latter. Thus, the electron donation from the phenolic oxygen to the copper(II) ion is decreased relative to that for (Cu-QSB-1,2 or 3-*o*-PhDA) when each oxygen coordinates to two metal ions, as in the case of [(Cu-QSB-1,2 and 3-*o*-PhDA)MX₂]. This may result in the increase of the ir frequency of the phenolic oxygen and blue-shift of the copper d-d bond. It can thus be concluded that the environment of copper(II) ion in bimolecular complexes is fully planar while other

metal ion is in a tetrahedral or pseudo-tetrahedral environment with no metal–metal interaction. Addition of water to these heterobinuclear complexes breaks the bridge resulting in the separation of (Cu-QSB-*o*-PhDA) and MX₂.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. H. B. Naik, Head, Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat, for providing facilities.

References

1. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT, JR and A. CHAKRAVORTI, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 7, 83.
2. U. CASELLATO, P. A. VIGATO and M. VIDALI, *Coord. Chem Rev.*, 1977, 23, 31.
3. J. J. GRZYBOWSKI, P. H. MERRILL and F. L. URBACH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, 17, 3078.
4. M. MIKURIYA, M. NAKAMURA, H. OKAWA and S. KIDA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, 70, 223.
5. *Ibid.*, 1983, 68, 111.
6. Y. NISHIDA, N. OISHI and S. KIDA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, 46, 69.
7. J. C. BROWN and J. C. WARDESKA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, 21, 1530.
8. E. SINN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 358.
9. B. C. WHITEMORE and R. EISENBERG, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, 22, 1.
10. P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 505.
11. J. J. GRZYBOWSKI and F. L. URBACH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 2604.
12. S. K. MANDAL and K. NAG, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 2429.
13. S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1967, 3, 496.
14. C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 2723.
15. Y. MUTO, M. KATO, H. B. JONASSEN and L. C. CUSACHS, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, 42, 417.
16. T. TOKII, Y. MUTO, M. KATO, K. IMAI and H. B. JONASSEN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 3377.
17. M. D. GLICK and R. L. LINTVEDT, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 21, 261.
18. B. T. THAKER and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 615.
19. P. B. THAKER and B. T. THAKER, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 24, 144.
20. D. H. BUSCH in 'Cobalt', ed. R. S. YOUNG, ACS Monograph Series, Reinhold, New York, 1960, Ch 6.
21. S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 1805.
22. R. H. HOLM and F. A. COTTON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, 31, 788.
23. L. SACCONI and M. CIAMPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 276.
24. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968, p. 356.
25. M. NAKAMURA, H. OKAWA and S. KIDA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, 62, 201.
26. T. TOKII, M. KANEKO, K. YAMANAKA, Y. MUTO and M. KATO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1979, 52, 3751.